

Some Observations on Magnesium Carbonate and its Double Carbonate containing Potassium

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Magnesium carbonate trihydrate, $MgCO_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ is formulated as $Mg(OH)(HCO_3) \cdot 2H_2O$ on the basis of thermogravimetric and infra-red spectral data. The potassium compounds, $KHCO_3$, $MgCO_3 \cdot 4H_2O$, has been studied by thermogravimetry and its infra-red spectra is recorded.

MAGNESIUM carbonate trihydrate, $MgCO_3 \cdot 3H_2O$, is formulated as $Mg(OH)(HCO_3) \cdot 2H_2O$ on the basis of thermogravimetric studies.¹⁻³ In order to get a more accurate information regarding the composition of the compound its infra-red spectra was recorded and reported in the present work. The compound was prepared from magnesium salt by using sodium bicarbonate⁴ and also through a new procedure utilising guanidino carbonate.

The potassium compound, $KHCO_3$, $MgCO_3 \cdot 4H_2O$, was prepared according to Berzelius⁵. It was studied by thermogravimetry and its infra-red spectra was recorded.

Experimental

Preparation of the carbonates of magnesium:

1. *Potassium hydrogen dicarbonatomagnesium hydrate, $KHMg(CO_3)_2 \cdot 4.5H_2O$.* Magnesium nitrate hexahydrate (11 g in 10 ml water) was added dropwise to 300 ml potassium bicarbonate (30%) with constant mechanical stirring when needle-shaped precipitate appeared. After half an hour the precipitate was filtered off, washed twice with cold water, dried between folds of filter paper and finally dried in air. Yield 4.3 g. (Found: Mg, 8.88, CO_2 33.56%; $KHMg(CO_3)_2 \cdot 4.5H_2O$ requires Mg, 9.16, CO_2 33.16%).

2. *Magnesium carbonate trihydrate, $MgCO_3 \cdot 3H_2O$.*

(a) Prepared by using sodium bicarbonate: Magnesium nitrate hexahydrate (11 g in 10 ml water) was added dropwise to 300 ml sodium bicarbonate (10%) with constant mechanical stirring for about 2 hr. The crystals (needle-shaped) were filtered off after 4 hr, washed twice with cold water and dried as above. Yield 2.6 g. (Found: Mg 17.60, CO_2 31.68%; $MgCO_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ requires Mg 17.56, CO_2 31.81%).

(b) Prepared by utilising guanidine carbonate. Magnesium nitrate hexahydrate (2.75 g in 30 ml

water) was added with constant mechanical stirring to a solution (175 ml) containing ammonium chloride (2 g) and ammonium carbonate (3.5 g). Then guanidine carbonate (4 g in 10 ml water) was added to the above solution. The crystals (needle-shaped) were filtered off after 4 hrs, washed twice with cold water and dried in air. Yield 0.6 g. (Found: Mg 18.27, CO_2 30.70%; $MgCO_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ requires Mg 17.58, CO_2 31.81%).

Thermogravimetric (TGA) studies: The data were recorded in a manually operated thermobalance by heating the compounds at the increasing rate of 2° per minute. In actual process small amount (near about 0.1 g) of the dry material was used for each thermogravimetric analysis. The sample was taken in a small platinum crucible of about 2 ml capacity. It was attached by a platinum wire to the left pan of an analytical balance (sensitivity 0.1 mg. and having damping arrangement) and was suspended into a vertical tube furnace. The temperature was controlled by a manually operated variac. The temperature of the furnace was allowed to rise at the rate of 2° per minute. The weight was directly read from the electrically illuminated scale situated at the base of the central pillar of the balance. The thermogravimetric curves were drawn by plotting weight loss (% loss) against temperature.

Results and Discussion

Thermogravimetric studies of $KHCO_3 \cdot MgCO_3 \cdot 4.5H_2O$:

The potassium compound was found to remain stable upto 50° (Fig. 1, Curve I); after that a rapid loss in weight (31.71%) between 80-100° took place, which corresponded to the loss of 4.5 molecules of water per mole of the compound. The compound then decomposed slowly with a horizontal at 300°-340° and after 400° again decomposed rapidly. A stable ultimate product (hygroscopic) is obtained

at 520°. The mode of thermal decomposition of the above compound may be represented as follows :

Thermogravimetric studies of MgCO₃·3H₂O :

The T.G. data for magnesium carbonate trihydrate prepared by using (i) sodium bicarbonate, and (ii) guanidine carbonate were found to be identical (Fig. 1, Curve II.). The compound remains stable below 100° and considerable decomposition takes place between 110° and 240°. Rapid decomposition is again observed above 400° and at 480° constancy in weight is noticed corresponding to the formation of MgO. The loss in weight (Found 26.12% and 38.90%) around 190°–200° and 350°–360° corresponds to the loss of two molecules of water and three molecules of water (Theoretical 26.02% and 39.04%) respectively from magnesium carbonate trihydrate.

Fig. 1. Thermograms of I—KHCO₃·MgCO₃·4.5H₂O ; II—MgCO₃·3H₂O.

On heating MgCO₃·3H₂O isothermally at 100° and 200° the observed loss in weight 16% and 33.1%

respectively were found to be close to those, viz., 17% and 35.5%, reported by Dell and Weller³ at those temperatures.

From the above data it may be concluded that out of the three molecules of water in MgCO₃·3H₂O two molecules of water remain as water of crystallisation and the other molecule of water remain as water of constitution.

Infra-red Spectral Studies :

The infra-red spectra of the potassium compound, KHCO₃·MgCO₃·4.5H₂O, show a broad band such as, 1460–75 cm⁻¹, characteristic for HCO₃⁻ group⁶. The presence of bidentate carbonate group^{7,8} cannot be ruled out in this compound, since the broad band in the region 1640–80 cm⁻¹ might be due to both H–O–H and CO₃²⁻ group.

The infra-red spectra of magnesium carbonate trihydrate show the frequencies 1425 cm⁻¹ and 1480 cm⁻¹, which are known to be characteristic frequencies for bicarbonate group⁶. Moreover, a band at 1535 cm⁻¹ suggest the compound to be a basic carbonate.^{9–12} The data, therefore, suggest that magnesium carbonate trihydrate should correctly be represented as magnesium hydroxobarbonate dihydrate, i.e., Mg(OH)(HCO₃)₂·2H₂O. The spectral data thus confirm the above representation of hydrated magnesium carbonate trihydrate as suggested by others^{1–3} from thermochemical measurements. The infra-red spectral data of Mg(OH)(HCO₃)₂·2H₂O agree well also with the data reported by Hunt *et al.*⁹ for basic magnesium carbonate. They, however, did not give any formula for the basic magnesium carbonate.

TABLE I—INFRA-RED SPECTRA OF DOUBLE CARBONATES OF POTASSIUM AND MAGNESIUM HYDRATE AND MAGNESIUM CARBONATE TRIHYDRATE

KHCO ₃ ·MgCO ₃ ·4.5H ₂ O	MgCO ₃ ·3H ₂ O	Probable band assignments
688–693(B,M) cm ⁻¹	695–708(B,W) cm ⁻¹	ν ₄ CO ₃
855(M)	857(S)	ν ₂ CO ₃
1150–1190(B,W)	—	ν CO ₃
1390(W)	—	ν CO ₃
—	1425(S)	ν CO ₃
1460–1475(B,S)	1480(S)	ν CO ₃
—	1530(S)	ν ₃ CO ₃
1640–1680(B,S)	1640–1675(B,M)	ν ₃ CO ₃ , δH ₂ O
3190–3450(B,S)	3300–3400(B,S)	ν OH
—	3600(S)	—

S = Strong, W = Weak, B = Broad, M = Medium.

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